

Some useful plant-derived drugs : importance of enantiomeric stereospecificity†

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Distinguished members of the audience, colleagues, friends and students,

I crave your indulgence to make some introductory remarks.

If we analyse broadly all the major scientific efforts of the past, and those which are currently underway and even those that are planned for the future we would find that all these are dedicated mainly to two major themes – the philosophical expressions of which we find in some poems of Rabindranath Tagore.

I quote –

“অচেনাকে চিনে চিনে উঠবে জীবন ভরে।”

To know the unknown and to unveil the mysteries of Nature are the most prominent, intellectual desires of human being. The more we know – more and more we want to know – and more and more we know – more and more remain unknown!

I quote Tagore –

“বিপুলা এ পৃথিবীর কতটুকু জানি!
..... কত নদী গিরি সিন্ধু মরু,
কত না অজানা জীব, কত না অপরিচিত তরু
রয়ে গেল অগোচরে!”

"How little we know of this vast world !
..... so many rivers, mountains, seas, deserts
So many unknown animals, so many unknown plants
Remain beyond our knowledge !"

Again I quote –

“শেষ নাই যে শেষ কথা কে বলবে!”

"There is no end, so who will tell the last word !"

The path of this quest is an endless one – the final answers are yet to be sought.

The other important theme is –

I quote again from Tagore –

“মরিতে চাহি না আমি সুন্দর ভুবনে,
মানবের মাঝে আমি বাঁচিবারে চাই।”

"I do not want to die in this beautiful world,
I want to live amongst the human beings."

It is to this theme – all the medical, biomedical biochemical, physiological, medicinal, pharmaceutical and certain types of chemical and physical researches are dedicated.

Myself along with my research collaborators in a very humble way remained associated with both the themes by way of discovering new natural products mostly of plant and some of marine origin and unveiling their chemical nature – during the last five decades or so.

Let me now come to the lecture topic.

Some useful plant-derived drugs

Ladies and gentlemen,

Since the major part of the audience possesses different shades of chemistry and some are from disciplines other than chemistry, I thought of not discussing hard-core organic chemistry to this gathering. I believe that such a talk might act as a lead balloon sinking in an ocean of disinterest.

Keeping this in mind I have selected a topic entitled "*Some useful plant-derived drugs : importance of enantiomeric stereospecificity.*" This is expected to be of much general interest and can be discussed in a popular way outskirting the chemical details. Even then certain chemical descriptors of the molecules could not be avoided and have to be incorporated.

I dedicate this lecture to the revered memory of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, the Founder-President of the Indian Chemical Society.

With the advent of civilization people started recording their observations and inferences on medicinal plants based

†Part 2 of the Presidential Address delivered at the first technical session of the 39th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Nagarjuna University, Nagarjunanagar, on December 23, 2002.

on the folklore and traditional medicine. Thus the earliest mention of the medicinal uses of plants is found in "Rig Veda" – the oldest repository of human knowledge, having been written between 4500 and 1600 BC. In the work that followed, particularly in 'Ayurveda' the properties of various crude drugs have been given in detail in *Caraka Samhitā* and *Susruta Samhitā* – written around after 1000 BC [P. Ray and H. N. Gupta, "Caraka Samhitā (A Scientific Synopsis)" Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 1965; P. Ray, H. N. Gupta and Mira Roy, "Susruta Samhitā (A Scientific Synopsis)", Indian National Science Academy, New Delhi, 1980]. The knowledge of medicinal plants accumulated in this way in course of many centuries. The different civilizations that came to India in the form of either invaders or friends, contributed to the development of vegetable drugs in India.

It is particularly appropriate at the present moment when the pharmaceutical concerns of the world are emitting a ceaseless flow of new synthetic drugs that *attention should be turned to the indigenous herbs of the world for the possible remedies of the sufferings of human being*. This is more so, since synthetic drugs in most cases have harmful side-effects.

Herbal drugs prefer the composite prescription (i.e. the combination of herbs and hence mixture of chemical constituents) rather than one or two active ingredients. Herbal drugs thus have synergetic therapeutic effect. However, randomized and controlled examination of different batches of a particular herbal drug in several cases show that they do not have same components to the same extent and show incompatibility in efficacy. Their compositions vary because of many factors: maturity of the plant, place of growth, season of collection etc. Thus standarization of herbal drugs poses a great problem. But mostly the herbal drugs, being natural ones, do not have adverse side-effects.

At present, we have at our disposal a formidable array of *modern drugs*^{1a,b}, but satisfactory therapy is available only for about one-third of all presently known ailments; thus the discovery and invention of new agents are genuinely and urgently needed^{1a}. Modern drug has been defined by Professor Sukh Dev^{1,2} as "*a clinically efficaceous (having undergone pharmacological, toxicological and clinical screening as per accepted parameters of modern medical sciences) chemical entity or mixture, of synthetic or natural origin, administered as such or admixed with other entities or vehicles, and being produced in a reproducible form under good analytical control.*"

With the advent of time and technology the structures

of natural products of profound biological activity were elaborated after their separation in the purest form, and a few of them were synthesized and modified to enhance their biological properties. Interests in folk and tribal remedies are ever-increasing with the hope of discovering drugs for incurable diseases like cancer, AIDS, diabetes, cardiovascular disorders and parasitic or viral diseases. Higher plants have been continuing to play a useful role in the development of modern therapeutic agents. The starting point for the utilization of a plant drug in modern medicine has been some reference to the use of that plant material as an indigenous cure, based on a folklore or traditional system of medicine of one culture or another. The ethnotherapeutics and some traditional modern drugs^{1a}, illustrated in Table 1 are convincing in this respect.

Table 1. Ethnotherapeutics and some traditional modern drugs*

Drug	Basis of investigation
Codeine, morphine (effective pain killers)	Opium, the latex of <i>Papaver somniferum</i> used by ancient Egyptians, Greeks and Sumerians for the treatment of headaches, arthritis and for inducing sleep
(±) Atropine [†] , (–) hyoscyamine (dilatation of pupil)	<i>Atropa belladonna</i> and <i>Hyoscyamus niger</i> were important drugs in Babylonian folklore. (Ladies of Venice used it for converting them into lustrous wide-eyed beauties)
Ephedrine (antiallergic, used for respiratory trouble)	Crude drug, Ma-huang (austere yellow) derived from <i>Ephedra sinica</i> had been used by the Chinese for respiratory ailments since 2700 BC
Quinine (antimaterial)	<i>Cinchona</i> species were used by Peruvian Indians for the treatment of fever
Colchicine (used for gout)	Use of <i>Colchicum</i> in the treatment of gout has been known in Europe since 78 AD
Emetine (used for amoebic dysentery)	Roots and rhizomes of <i>Ipecacuanha</i> were used by the Brazilian Indians and several other S. American tribes to induce vomiting and cure dysentery
Digoxin (used for heart ailments)	<i>Digitalis</i> leaves were being used in Europe in heart therapy during the 18th century
Reserpine (excellent tranquilizer)	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> ("Sarpagandha") roots were widely used in India for the treatment of hypertension, insomnia and mental disorder

*Source : Ref. 1a.

[†]In modern medicine atropine is classified as an anticholinergic drug which means, it is an inhibitor of meat-stimulated gastric juice.

A bird's eye view of the stereostructures of some extremely useful bioactive molecules^{1,3} (Fig. 1.) like

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reserpine, vinblastine, vincristine, a few lignans like teniposide, etoposide, podophyllotoxin etc.; taxol and its synthetic analogue taxotere; camptothecin and related compounds, artemisinin, artemether and arteether; some other drugs from Indian and Chinese plants like yingzhaosu A and yingzhaosu C, gomisin A, huperzine A, huperzine B, sophoradin, plaunotol, plaunol etc.; and active principles of some plants of Ayurvedic literature, e.g., *Z-guggulsterone* and *E-guggulsterone*, andrographolide, picroside-I and

picroside- II, gedunin, palasonin, psoralen, bakuchiol etc. – their plant sources and their bioactivities^{1,3} are presented in brief in Table 2. Leading references regarding first isolation, structure elucidation/synthesis and bioactivity have been cited in the last column, as far as possible.

In almost all cases outstanding results have been obtained essentially confirming claims regarding many traditional Indian (*cf.* Ayurvedic *materia medica*) and Chinese drugs of plant origin (Chinese Pharmacopoeia, 1990). Professor

Table 2. The sources and bioactivities* of some useful natural molecules

Name (structure no.)	Source (plant)	Effective for the treatment of/activity	Reference
Reserpine (1) (CIBA, USA, 1953) (Indole alkaloid)	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (Sans. : <i>Sarpagandha</i>)	Hypertension, mental disorder; used as tranquilizer	4–6
Vinblastine (2) (Eli Lilly, 1961)	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (Syn : <i>Vinca roseus</i>)	Hodgkin's disease, lymphosarcoma,	7, 8
Vincristine (3) (Eli Lilly, 1963) (Dimeric indole alkaloids)	(Beng. : <i>Nayantara</i>) (few hundred mg from few tons of dried plant materials)	leukemia in children	9, 10
Podophyllotoxin (4)	<i>Podophyllum hexandrum</i> , <i>P. peltatum</i>	Antimitotic, anticancer but toxic	11–13
Teniposide (5) Etoposide (6) (Lignans)	Developed from podophyllotoxin	Testicular cancer, small cell lung cancer and lymphomas	
Taxol (7) (Paclitaxol)	<i>Taxus brevifolia</i> , Yew tree (bark)	Metastatic ovarian cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, malignant melanoma	14–18
Taxotere (8) (Diterpenoids)	Semisynthetic analogue of taxol	As active as taxol	
Camptothecin (10) (Quinoline alkaloid)	<i>Camptotheca acuminata</i> (Chinese tree)(bark) <i>Nothapodytes nimmoniana</i> (Syn : <i>Mappia foetida</i>) (Indian tree)	Antileucoplastic activity with serious side-effects, such as bleeding in bladder	21–23
Irenotecan (11) Topotecan (12) 9-Aminocamptothecin (13)	} Synthetic analogues of camptothecin	Lung, ovarian, colon, cervical cancer(11) Similar effects(12,13)	24
Artemisinin (14) (Sesquiterpene peroxide lactone, introduced world-wide in 1987)	<i>Artemisia annua</i> (herb) (used traditionally in China against fever)	Effective against cerebral malaria; active against both chloroquine-sensitive and chloroquine-resistant strains of <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i> and <i>P. vivax</i>	25–28
Artemether (15) Arteether (16)	Simple derivatives of artemisinin	Have better clinical profile and now are being actively developed	25–28
Yingzhaosu A (17) Yingzhaosu C (18) (Sesquiterpene peroxides)	<i>Artabotrys uncinatus</i> (roots) (used in China for malaria)	Like artemisinin	28
Gomisin A (19) (Polyoxygenated biphenyl derivative)	<i>Schizandra chinensis</i> (fruits) (used in China for stomach trouble)	Hepatoprotective	29–31

Table-2 (contd.)

Sophoradin (20) (Chalcone)	<i>Sophora substrata</i>	Significant antigastric ulcer activity	1
Plaunotol (21) (Acyclic diterpene)	<i>Croton sulyrantus</i> Thai medicinal plant 'plau-noi'	Cytoprotective antiulcer agent	1
Plaunol (22)	<i>C. sublyratus</i> , <i>C. columnaris</i> (Thai species)	Antipeptic ulcer activity	32
Huperzine A (23)	<i>Huperzia serrata</i> (used in China to alleviate memory disorders of the old)	Alzheimer disease; powerful acetylcholine esterase (Ach E) inhibitor	33–35
Huperzine B (24)	<i>H. serrata</i>	Marked anticholinesterase activity	36, 37

From some Ayurvedic plants receiving clinical support for their therapeutic claims :

Z-Guggulsterone (25)	Gum-resin called 'gugglu', (renowned in Ayurveda) from <i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Syn : <i>C. mukul</i>)	Inhibits cholesterol biosynthesis	38, 39
E-Guggulsterone (26)	<i>C. wightii</i>	Similar activity	38, 39
Andrographolide (27) (a diterpene)	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (<i>Bhuinimka</i>)	Chronic hepatitis; liver cirrhosis	40–42
Picoside-I (28)	<i>Picrorrhiza kurroa</i>	Hepatoprotector	43
Picoside-II (29) (Monoterpene glucosides)	<i>P. kurroa</i>	liver ailments	44
Psoralen (30) (a furocoumarin)	<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>	Antileucoderma, antibacterial (stimulates formation of melanin)	45, 46
Bakuchiol (31) (C ₁₂ -side-chain carrying <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzene)	<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>	Antibacterial, effective against psoriasis	1, 47–49
Palasonin (32)	<i>Butea frondosa</i> (Sans. : <i>Palasha</i>)	Anthelmintic activity	50, 51
Gedunin (33) (a tetranortriterpenoid)	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> (Sans. : <i>nimb</i> Beng. : <i>neem</i>)	Antimalarial agent; good <i>in vitro</i> activity on certain clones of <i>Plasmodium falciparum</i>	52–55

*Also references 1a, 3.

Sukh Dev has discussed 'Ayurveda : potential and opportunity' in some detail¹.

Strategies for drug development

Because of the importance of taxol (7) and its analogues I would like to deal with them a little more to illustrate strategies for drug development. Following a systematic screening programme for new anticancer compounds by NIH (USA), the structure and antileukemic activity of taxol, isolated from the bark of the pacific yew tree, *Taxus brevifolia* were first reported¹⁴ in 1971. Intense research activities followed and the development of taxol as an anti-cancer drug (Table 3)¹⁸ had been suffering hindrance due to the problem of obtaining sufficient supplies of taxol. The bark from two trees barely yielded enough taxol for treating

Table 3. The development of taxol as an anticancer drug*

1962–66	US National Cancer Institute (NCI) programme of natural product screening for cytotoxicity and anti-leukemic activity
1969	Pure taxol isolated
1971	Wani and Wall report the antileukemic activity of taxol
1979	Susan Horwits reports that taxol stimulates microtubule assembly
1983–90	Phase I and phase II clinical trials for all types of cancer; most favourable results obtained for breast and ovarian cancer
1991	US NCI initiate to develop taxol as an anticancer drug
1991–95	Further extensive hospital trials and application for US Federal Drug Administration approval
1994	The first total synthesis of taxol by Nicolaou and Holton

*Source : Ref. 18.

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Fig. 1. The stereostructures of some useful bioactive molecules.

Fig. 1 (contd.). The stereostructures of some useful bioactive molecules.

a single patient for breast/ovarian cancer. Yew trees being very slow-growing (life : several hundred years) and because yew wood was used for making bows, they were planted in church yards to protect them from animals. Rhone-Poulenc (France) and Bristol Myers-Squibb (US) (trade name paclitaxol) had started to supply taxol to limited extent for use in the clinic.

The first total synthesis of taxol independently by Nicolaou¹⁵ and Holton¹⁶ in 1994 involved *ca* 30 steps. Danishefsky¹⁷ achieved its synthesis by a slightly shorter route in 1995. But each route is time-consuming and gives less than 5 p.c. yield. However, they led to the synthesis of some important taxol analogues with potential activity.

Potier and his colleagues isolated large amounts of 10-deacetylbaccatin III (which is taxol **7** with OH at C-10 instead of the side-chain) from the leaves of the European yew without affecting the trees and subsequently attached the side-chain by chemical synthesis¹⁹. They also found that a taxol derivative, taxotere (**8**) carrying a different side-chain protecting group at nitrogen was as active as taxol.

Researches went on to increase the effectiveness of taxol by converting it to a derivative which will reach the site of action (microtubules) in the cancer cells. Such derivatives or prodrugs are used to protect the drug from being deactivated by chemical reactions occurring during their passage through the body. One promising taxol prodrug is the phosphate derivative (**9**) developed by Bristol -Myers Squibb. The hydrophilic phosphate group makes the compound water-soluble and enzymes in the body hydrolyse the ester group at C-7 to release taxol to cancerous cells.

A US biotech company (Genentech) has developed an alternative compound designated Protax²⁰ – a β -lactamase is attached to the antibody effectively which targets the drug to release taxol. Thus semisynthesis provides a drug more potent than taxol.

Continued investigation of Nature's drugstore for fascinating natural products is expected to give better drugs for all types of cancer and other incurable diseases in near future.

Table 4. *Aloe* medicine cabinet*

Ingredients [¶]	Effects
<i>Vitamins</i> A, B (thiamine), B ₂ (riboflavin), B ₃ (niacin), trace of B ₁₂ (usually available from only animal sources), C, E, choline and folic acid	Synergetic effect, important antioxidant effects
<i>Enzymes</i> : biochemical catalysts, e.g. amylase and lipase, a carboxypeptidase – a peptide associated with perception of pain	Aiding digestion by breaking down fats and sugars thus elicits a valuable analgesic and anti-inflammatory effect
<i>Minerals</i> : Na, K, Cd, Mg, Mn, Cu, Zn, Cr, Fe; magnesium acetate inhibits histamine decarboxylation preventing formation of histamine from histidine	In allergic reactions certain cells release histamine into skin leading to intense pain and itching – accounting for <i>Aloe's</i> powerful anti-itching effect
<i>Sugars</i> : both mono- and polysaccharides (comprising mainly glucose and mannose) –absorbed completely and appear in the bloodstream unchanged	Acts as immunomodulators, capable of both enhancing and retarding immune response
<i>Sterols</i> : like cholesterol, campesterol, β -sitosterol and lupeol	Anti-inflammatory effect for treating rheumatoid arthritis and asthma (Polysaccharides also have similar effects)
<i>Amino acids</i> : 20 of 22 amino acids required by the human body; 7 of the essential amino acids (excepting tryptophan) that the body cannot synthesise and have to be taken along with food	
<i>Anthraquinones</i> : in the free state and their derivatives : barbaloin (10-(11, 51-anhydroglucosyl)aloe-emodin-9-anthrone); isobarbaloin, anthrone-C-glycosides and chromones – can absorb UV light and inhibit tyrosinase activity	In large amount the anthraquinones exert powerful purgative effect; in small doses they are potent antimicrobial agents and possess analgesic effects; reduce melanin formation (hyperpigmentation)
<i>Liginin</i> : inert woody substance	Endows unique penetrative ability taking other active ingredients deep into the skin
<i>Saponins</i> : these soapy substances form 3% of the gel	General cleansers with antiseptic properties
<i>Salicylic acid</i>	Possesses anti-inflammatory and antibacterial properties

*Source : Ref. 56.

¶Although the amount of each ingredient is very small, the apparent healing effect of this plant comes from synergetic effect of all components working in tandem.

I am now tempted to devote some time to discuss about the constituents of green tea leaves followed by the various uses and healing effect of *Aloe* plants.

Green tea contains (-)-epicatechin gallate and (-)-epigallocatechin gallate. H. Nakane of Aichi Cancer Research Centre in Nagoya, Japan, has reported that these two compounds and their oxidation products in black green tea are potent HIV inhibitors.

Aloe plants : 300 species are known. Over years they are known as 'First Aid Plant', 'Medicine Plant', 'Miracle Plant', 'Plant of Life' and 'Wand of Heaven'. Four main species have medicinal properties : *A. barbdensis*, *A. perryi*, *A. fexus*, and *A. arborescence* (cactus-like plant familiar to the deserts of Africa and Arizona). *Aloea vera* gel is obtained by extraction of leaves of *Aloe* plant, especially of mature *A. barbadensis* leaves; (each leaf weighs ca 500 – 700 g). *Aloe* comes from the Arab word *Alloeh*, meaning bitter substance. The gel's effect on the skin is as a healing and antiaging agent because of its moisturising and reduction of wrinkle effect. It has been used as a beauty and medical aid for thousands of years. Every week or so a new cream or cosmetic containing *Aloe vera* is likely to come to the market. Egyptian queens Nefertiti and Cleopatra were users of *A. vera* which is regarded as the source of their beauty.

Aloe medicine cabinet (Table 4) gives detailed information regarding its constituents and medicinal effects⁵⁶.

Enantiomeric stereospecificity; the dimensions of drug stereoselectivity

The bioactive molecules of Nature including plants, animals or insects are referred to as secondary metabolites from the viewpoint of their biogenetic origin in the cells. They are formed from simpler molecules called precursors or primary metabolites present in the cells – equivalent to synthons in organic synthesis – by an integrated network of enzymatically catalysed and genetically controlled reactions. In fact, enzymes, formed from L-amino acids only, barring glycine (i.e. α -aminoacetic acid), are themselves single enantiomers and hence the stereorecognition is the hallmark of enzymes and stereospecificity is maintained to generate single enantiomers only. Thus most of the bioactive natural molecules are chiral molecules and Nature synthesises them in stereospecific fashions yielding a particular enantiomer.

Although many of the plant-derived drugs of major importance to the health and well-being of mankind have been synthesized, a very few are produced commercially by synthesis. Thus the plant sources remain extremely important, not only in producing drugs, but also in providing

novel biologically active model compounds leading to the pursuit for the development of potentially more potent and less toxic drugs.

In recent years interest in chiral synthesis of pure enantiomers has gained new impetus as a result of the increasing awareness of the importance of enantiomeric purity in the context of biological activity. Indeed many drugs (as well as pesticides and food additives etc.) are chiral and therefore exist as two enantiomers (or more stereoisomers) which, from the viewpoint of biological activity, should be considered as different substances. In fact, the drug regulatory agencies are issuing guidelines for drug evaluation, development and registration that explicitly recognise racemate drugs as being composed of distinct entities. This is due to the formation of diastereomeric complexes between chiral drugs and drug receptors (in living organisms) like enzymes, membranes etc. made up of chiral molecules such as amino acids, carbohydrates, triglycerides and so on.

Thus stereospecific biogenesis of bioactive molecules and the enantiomeric stereospecificity of natural as well as synthetic drugs can be visualised in a very simple way⁵⁷ as shown in Fig. 2, although the actual pathway is more complex.

Fig. 2. A simple model displaying the complimentary recognition mechanism between the receptor and the potential substrate.

Many examples of enantiospecificity (i.e. stereospecificity exhibited by enantiomeric substrates) are known, where one enantiomer has the desired activity but the other is inactive or have toxic or other effects or remain yet unscreened. More than 50% of the commercial drugs available worldwide have stereogenic centers. Even today,

Category 1

Sodium monoglutamate
 (S)-(-) Meat flavour
 (R)-(+) Insipid

Acetyl- β -methylcholine
 R-(+)-Enantiomer Muscular activity : 230
 S-(-)-Enantiomer 1

(+)-Ascorbic acid
 Curative properties against scurvy

(-)-Ascorbic acid
 Inactive

α -Phenoxypropionic acid
 D, (R)
 Herbicidal activity

α -Phenoxypropionic acid
 L, (S)
 No herbicidal activity; has undesirable ecological impact

(+)-Estrone
 Sexual hormone

(-)-Estrone
 Inactive

2-Propyl-4-pentenol acid
 (R) : No teratogenic activity (S) : Teratogenic

(+)-Pilocarpine (3S, 4R)
 Reduces Intraocular pressure (glaucoma)

(-)-Pilocarpine (3R, 4S)
 (+)-Isopilocarpine (3R, 4R)
 No such activity

(R)-(+)-Mevalonic acid
 Biogenetic precursor of secondary metabolites

(S)-(-)-Mevalonic acid
 Not incorporated by biological systems

R = H : (-)-Morphine
 R = Me : (-)-Codeine

(-)-Morphine is a powerful analgesic and narcotic; hence its major use is only for terminal pain.³

(-)-Codeine is also analgesic (potency 1/10 of (-)-morphine), but non-addictive; also used for preventing coughing.³

(+)-Morphine
 (+)-Codeine

(+)-Morphine has no such activity

(+)-Codeine has no such activity

Fig. 3. Contrasting biological behaviour exhibited by enantiomeric substrates (exhibiting stereospecificity).

Category 1 (contd.)

Metabolites of benzo[A]pyrene
 (+)-Isomer Carcinogen (-)-Isomer Innocuous

(*S*)-(-)-Propranolol (*R*)-(+)-Propranolol
 β-Blocker at β-adrenoceptors

Potency : 40

1

Category 2

Asparagine
L,(*S*)-Enantiomer Bitter *D*,(*R*)-Enantiomer Sweet

(-)-Nicotine (2*S*) (Natural) Insecticidal property, highly toxic (man)
 (+)-Nicotine (2*R*) (Cigarette smoke) Different activity (Not properly assessed)

(*S*),(*S*)-Ethambutol Tuberculostatic (*R*),(*R*)-Ethambutol Causes blindness

Antipodal barbituric acid derivatives
R = Buⁿ : Narcotic Anticonvulsant (MBPB)
R = Prⁿ : Anesthetic Convulsant (MPPB)

L,(*R*)-Penicillamine Mutagen *D*,(*S*)-Penicillamine Antiarthritic

1-Chloro-2,3-propanediol
 (*R*) Poison (*S*) Medicinal drug

(*S*)-Ketamine Anaesthetic (*R*)-Ketamine Hallucinogen

(*S*)-Dopa Anti-Parkinson (*R*)-Dopa Serious side effects

Fig. 3 (contd.). Contrasting biological behaviour exhibited by enantiomeric substrates (exhibiting stereospecificity).

Category 2 (contd.)

Category 3

The (R),(R)-enantiomer is more hepatotoxic than the racemate

The (S),(R)-diastereomer is an α_1 -blocker

Category 4

- i) For some local anesthetic and antiarrhythmic activities the enantiomers are essentially equipotent
- ii) For 2-propyl-4-pentenoic acid (*vide infra*) no stereoselectivity of aniconvulsant activity was observed

Fig. 3 (contd.). Contrasting biological behaviour exhibited by enantiomeric substrates (exhibiting stereospecificity)

some commercial drugs with stereogenic center/s in the molecule are sold as a racemic mixture, though the desired activity resides in one enantiomer

Enantiomers may differ both quantitatively and qualitatively in their biological activities. At one extreme, one enantiomer may be devoid of any biological activity, at the other extreme, both enantiomers may have qualitatively different biological activities. Thus, stereoselective differences may arise not only from drug interactions at pharmacological receptors, but also from pharmacokinetic events, including protein binding, and drug metabolism and transport^{58,59}. Because the undesired enantiomer may be a medicinal pollutant or an unscreened substance, endeavors have been going on all over the world during the past two decades or so to achieve chiral synthesis of the desired enantiomer (or stereoisomer) in cases of all known or new drugs starting from appropriate chiral synthons from natural sources.

In principle, the stereoisomers may differ in biological activities in several ways^{58,59}

Category

- 1) The enantiomers differ quantitatively in their

biological activities, in the extreme case one isomer is totally devoid of the measured bioactivity

- 2) The enantiomers differ qualitatively in their activities and exhibit different bioactivities at the same or different receptors
- 3) The racemate exhibits different behaviour compared to that of either enantiomer alone
- 4) Both (all) isomers are equally active and no stereoselectivity of interaction is observed. This situation is rarely observed even general anesthetics show stereoselectivity, although of moderate magnitude

Examples of all the above four categories, resulting from pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic considerations, are known. Enantiomeric stereospecificity are illustrated with a number of bioactive molecules, both synthetic and natural (Fig 3) (*cf* Refs 51–59). The majority of the natural drugs are available in a single stereoisomeric form, while the majority of the semi-synthetic or totally synthetic drugs used to be synthesized in racemic forms. However, the extent of availability of synthetic single enantiomer chiral drugs is increasing. In 1982 nearly 15% of synthetic racemic drugs

were available in single enantiomers; by 1991 this had increased to ≈40%. At present, it is likely to have increased significantly because of the decisions (i) to pursue single enantiomers rather than racemates, (ii) to switch the existing racemic drugs to single enantiomers.

The present global sales (\$ billion) of enantiopure drugs^{58b} of different categories are as follows: cardiovascular 11.3; antibiotics 10.8; hormones 4.5; central nervous system 2.0; anti-inflammatory 1.5; anticancer 1.0; others 4.5.

More than sixty existing racemic drugs may soon be produced as a single enantiomer (Table 5).

Table 5. Existing racemic drugs that may be produced as a single enantiomer*

Cardiovascular system (ca 30):
<i>e.g.</i> acebutolol, disopyramide, dobutamine, nicardipine, verapamil
Central nervous system (ca. 12):
<i>e.g.</i> fluoxetine, lorazepam, meclizine
Respiratory system (ca. 3):
<i>e.g.</i> albuterol, terbutaline
Anti-inflammatory (ca. 16):
<i>e.g.</i> cicloprofen, ibuprofen, ketoprofen
Antihistamines:
<i>e.g.</i> terfenadine

*Source: Ref. 58a.

Before I conclude I would like to quote Professor V. Prelog, N. L., who duly emphasised the significance of natural product chemistry⁶¹.

I quote – "Every natural product, which has appeared during the 3 billion years of evolution and survived, carries in its structure a message and many of them have a yet unrevealed function. To decipher the message, and to find out their function will remain for a long time one of the most challenging tasks of chemistry."

Thank you all for your kind patient attention.

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